

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COMPASSION AND EMPATHY LEVELS OF MIDWIFERY STUDENTS AND THEIR ATTITUDES TOWARDS INFERTILITY EBELİK ÖĞRENCİLERİNİN MERHAMET VE EMPATİ DÜZEYLERİ İLE İNFERTİLİTEYE YÖNELİK TUTUMLARI ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİ

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Infertility is significant psychosocial issue that can cause individuals to experience negative emotions, including stress, anxiety, anger, depression, and hopelessness. Patients coping with these challenges expect healthcare providers to approach them with empathy and compassion. It is crucial that students who take their first steps as healthcare team members remain sensitive to this issue. The objective of this study is to investigate the correlation between the levels of compassion and empathy of midwifery students and their attitudes towards infertility.

Methods: This descriptive and cross-sectional study used descriptive information form, Empathic Tendency Scale (ETS), Compassion Scale (CS) and Attitudes toward Infertility Scale (ATIS) for data collection.

Results: The results showed that the mean scores for ETS, CS, and ATIS among first-year midwifery students were 68.65±7.12, 96.21±10.85, and 50.90±6.25, respectively. A statistically significant relationship was found between the scores obtained from the ATIS, the CS, and the kindness and consciously sharing dimensions of the CS (p<0.005).

Conclusion: A statistically significant relationship was found between the scores obtained from the ATIS, the CS, and the kindness and consciously sharing dimensions of the CS.

Keywords: Attitudes, Empathy, Compassion, Infertility, Nursing

ÖZET

Amaç: İnfertilite, bireylerin stres, kaygı, öfke, depresyon ve umutsuzluk gibi olumsuz duygular yaşamasına neden olabilen önemli bir psikososyal sorundur. Bu zorluklarla başa çıkan bireyler, sağlık hizmeti sunucularının kendilerine empati ve merhamet yaklaşmalarını beklemektedir. Sağlık ekibinin bir üyesi olma yolunda ilk adımlarını atan öğrencilerin bu konuya karşı duyarlı olmaları büyük önem taşımaktadır. Bu çalışmanın amacı, ebelik öğrencilerinin merhamet ve empati düzeyleri ile infertiliteye yönelik tutumları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesidir.

Yöntem: Tanımlayıcı ve kesitsel nitelikteki bu çalışmada veri toplamak amacıyla Tanıtıcı Bilgi Formu, Empatik Eğilim Ölçeği (EEÖ), Merhamet Ölçeği (MÖ) ve İnfertiliteye Yönelik Tutum Ölçeği (İYTÖ) kullanılmıştır.

Bulgular: Birinci sınıf ebelik öğrencilerinin EEÖ, MÖ ve İYTÖ puan ortalamaları sırasıyla 68,65±7,12, 96,21±10,85 ve 50,90±6,25 olarak bulunmuştur. İYTÖ'den elde edilen puanlar ile MÖ toplam puanı ve MÖ'nün nezaket ve bilinçli paylaşım alt boyutları arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir ilişki bulunmuştur (p<0,005).

Sonuç: İnfertiliteye yönelik tutum ile merhamet düzeyi ve merhametin nezaket ve bilinçli paylaşım boyutları arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir ilişki saptanmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Tutum, Empati, Merhamet, İnfertilite, Hemşirelik

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INTRODUCTION

Infertility is the inability of a couple to achieve pregnancy over an average period of one year (in a woman under 35 years of age) or six months (in a woman above 35 years of age) despite adequate, regular (3-4 times per week), unprotected sexual intercourse (Cağlar & Yesiltepe, 2020; Güner Emül & Avsar, 2021). According to the data of the World Health Organization-World Health Organization (WHO) it is estimated that more than 80 million people worldwide are affected by infertility (World Health Organization (WHO), 2020). About 9% of men and 10% of women aged 15 to 44 reported infertility problems in the United States (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), 2020). Infertility is a sensitive case for which couples need the help of healthcare professionals who have the necessary knowledge, as well as the supporting and empathic approach. Midwives, who are the first healthcare professionals with whom couples communicate during and after the treatment, play a very important role in the coordination of the different stages of the treatment and in ensuring couples' commitment to the treatment (Cakır et al., 2020). Attitudes of midwives, can affect their perspectives, professional attitudes, and roles. Midwives, must be aware of their own feelings about infertility and keep these emotions under control to be able to help infertile couples. Midwives, exhibiting a positive attitude resulting from their knowledge can reduce the physiological, emotional, psychological, sexual problems and social negativities infertile couples experience because of infertility (Cağlar & Yesiltepe, 2020; Cakır et al., 2020). It is crucial for midwives, to plan and implement their midwifery approaches after they identify their own knowledge levels and attitudes, upon graduation and before they start their professional careers so that they can provide positive care and counseling services to infertile couples. Considered by the World Health Organization (WHO) as an important global health problem affecting all societies worldwide, infertility is defined as the failure of couples to achieve pregnancy within 12 months of regular sexual intercourse without using any family planning method (Vander Borgh & Wyns, 2018; WHO, 2020). Approximately 8-12% of couples in reproductive age worldwide are affected by infertility (WHO, 2020). According to Turkish Population and Health Research results (2013), 11.2% of married women aged 15-49 in Turkey are unlikely to have children. Infertility can be a challenging process that affects individuals financially, psychologically, and physically, as well as couples' relationships with each other (Assaysh-Öberg et al., 2023; Caglar & Yesiltepe, 2020; CDC, 2020; Hocaoglu, 2019). In Turkey, where cultural norms associate femininity with motherhood and masculinity with productivity, infertility can have a negative impact on the mental health and quality of life of couples and result with depression, anxiety, anger and hopelessness (Guner Emul & Avsar, 2021; Logan et al., 2019;). During the challenging process of infertility, individuals require healthcare professionals who can empathize with them, provide a sense of support, and maintain open communication (Akgul, 2023; Assaysh-Öberg et al., 2023; Ebrahimzadeh-Zagami, et al., 2020).

Compassion, a core value in healthcare, is defined as the desire to understand and alleviate the suffering and misfortune of others. It includes a sensitivity to the suffering of others, a willingness to help find a solution to the current situation, and to improve the well-being of the person suffering (Bray et al., 2014; Bloomfield & Pegram, 2015; Thiel et al., 2021; Vick et al., 2017; Yiğitbas et al., 2019). It is a state of benevolence and awareness of one's own or others' distress, with a willingness to eliminate this distress and take action (Nas & Sak, 2020). Consequently, compassion is the empathic response to suffering (Cingöl et al., 2018). Empathy, another core concept in nursing, is the ability to understand the feelings and thoughts of others. Individuals with a strong sense of compassion may also possess high levels of empathic skills (Özcan, 2012, Özdelikara & Babur, 2020)

Midwifery is a profession recognized for the intense emotions experienced by its practitioners. Midwives may feel compassion in situations such as loneliness, death, despair, or physical or emotional injury while caring for their patients. In addition to scientific knowledge, human relations are also crucial in nursing (Babadağ, 2010; Cingöl et al., 2018). Nursing care involves empathy, compassion, altruism, respect, and spiritual care, centers on helping others and internalizes sensitive love (Vander & Wan, 2019). When midwives approach individuals with an empathetic attitude, they can understand their needs and provide better quality care. Compassion, demonstrated through empathy, can enhance the quality of healthcare (Polat & Erdem, 2017). Empathic skills and disposition are now recognized as trainable abilities in nursing education. Therefore, while these traits are inherent to individuals, it is crucial to acquire and reinforce them through vocational education and professional practice.

In Turkey, graduates from midwifery departments typically work in family health centers, public hospitals, and In Vitro Fertilization (IVF) centers, as well as in all areas where women receive services (Karacam & Eroğlu, 2019). The goal of midwifery education is to train students as professionals with the necessary knowledge, skills, and values to understand and communicate effectively with patients, and to establish a therapeutic relationship with them. Therefore, it is crucial to measure the empathetic tendency, compassion, and sensitivity levels of students during the education process, which is the final step before entering the profession. This study aims to evaluate the relationship between midwifery students' levels of compassion and empathy and their attitudes towards infertility.

Research questions include the followings:

- What are the levels of compassion among midwifery students?
- What are the levels of empathy among midwifery students?
- What are the attitudes of midwifery students towards infertility?
- Is there a correlation between the levels of compassion and empathy among midwifery students and their attitudes towards infertility?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Purpose and Type of Research

This study used a descriptive, cross-sectional study design.

Population and Sample of the Study

The study population comprised all 109 first-year students enrolled in the midwifery program at Mersin University Health Science Faculty. No sampling was conducted. The study included voluntary midwifery students who were 18 years of age or older, attended school during the spring semester of the 2022-2023 academic year and had not previously taken departmental courses. The study was completed with the participation of 102 first-year midwifery students.

Data Collection and Analysis

Descriptive information form

This form was developed by the researchers based on the literature and included seven questions gather descriptive information about midwifery students, such as age, education level, income status, and family type (Cağlar & Yesiltepe, 2020; Guner Emul & Avşar, 2021).

Empathic Tendency Scale (ETS)

The ETS was developed by Dökmen (1988). The scale comprises 20 items, which are scored on a five-point Likert scale. Possible scores range from 20 to 100, with higher scores

indicating a greater empathic tendency. The Cronbach's alpha of the original scale and our study were both 0.79.

Compassion Scale (CS)

The CS was originally developed by Pommier (2011) and adapted into Turkish by Akdeniz and Deniz (2016). The 24-item scale consists of six dimensions, namely kindness (items 6,8,16,24), indifference (items 2,12,14,18), common humanity (items 11,15,17,20), separation (items 3,5,10,22), mindfulness (items 4,9,13,21) and disengagement (items 1,7,19,23). Items are scored on a five-point Likert scale and the scores obtained from the indifference, separation and disengagement dimensions are reverse-scored. Possible scores range from 24 to 120, with higher scores indicating higher level of compassion. The Cronbach's alpha of the Turkish version of the CS was 0.85. The Cronbach's alpha in our study was 0.84.

Attitudes toward infertility scale (ATIS)

The ATIS was developed by Siyez et al. (2018) and consists of 12 items, which are scored on a five-point Likert scale. Possible scores range from 1 to 60, with higher scores indicating positive attitudes towards infertility. The Cronbach's alpha of the original scale and our study were 0.89 and 0.84, respectively.

Researchers determined the time and place of the main course, which was compulsory for all first-year nursing students and obtained permission from the lecturer of the course. At the beginning of the first class, participants were informed about the aim of the study and informed consent form was obtained. Participants were then asked to complete the data collection tool, which took approximately 10-15 minutes.

SPSS version 27.0 was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics, including number, frequency, mean, standard deviation and minimum and maximum values, were used to present data on descriptive characteristics of the participants. Since Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed normal distribution, an independent samples t-test was used to compare two groups, and an ANOVA variance test was used to compare more than two groups. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.005$.

Limitations of the Study

Our study has some limitations. Firstly, the results are limited to the research sample and cannot be generalized to all university students. Secondly, since the ATIS has been recently developed in 2018, the number of studies that used the scale is limited.

Ethical Aspects of the Research

Ethical approval was obtained from the Clinical Sciences Ethics Committee of Toros University (No.65, Date, 2023). Participants were informed about the aim of the study and ensured that they could withdraw at any time. Verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants. The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

RESULTS

The students had a mean age of 20.14 ± 1.24 years. The majority of them resided in cities in the Eastern Anatolia and Mediterranean regions. All of the students were single and female, and 92.2% of them had an income equal to or greater than their expenses (Table1).

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics

Characteristics (n=102)	n	%
Age [$\bar{X} \pm S.D.$ →20.10±1.12 (years)]		
≤20	67	65.7
>20	35	34.3
Region of residence		
Eastern Anatolia		
Mediterranean	44	43.1
Central Anatolia	44	43.1
Southeast Anatolia	7	6.9
	7	6.9
Income level		
Less than expenses	8	7.8
Equal to & more than expenses	94	92.2

The mean scores obtained from the ETS, ATIS and CS were 68.65±7.12, 50.90±6.25 and 96.21±10.85, respectively. The mean scores obtained from the kindness, indifference, common humanity, separation, mindfulness and disengagement dimensions of the CS were 15.96±2.57, 8.49±2.99, 14.98±3.20, 7.86±2.45, 15.35±2.35 and 7.74±2.38, respectively (Table 2) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Scale Dimensions (Mean ± SD)

Table 2 shows a statistically significant difference between the ETS scores and the age group ($t=-3.761$; $p<0.001$). Students over 20 years old obtained significantly higher ETS scores than those under 20. As for the CS scores, there was a statistically significant difference between the region of residence and the score obtained from the separation dimension of the CS ($\chi^2=9.660$; $p=0.008$). The Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparison results indicated that students from the Eastern Anatolia region scored higher on the separation dimension than those from the Mediterranean and other regions of Turkey. Additionally, a statistically significant difference was found between the region of residence and the score obtained from the disengagement dimension of the CS ($\chi^2=10.750$; $p=0.005$). The Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparison results indicated that students from the Eastern Anatolia region scored higher on the disengagement dimension than those from the Mediterranean and other regions of Turkey. There was also a statistically significant difference in total CS scores based on region of residence ($F=7.792$; $p<0.001$). The Tukey's pairwise comparisons revealed that the total CS scores of participants from the Eastern Anatolia region were significantly lower than those of students from the Mediterranean and other regions of Turkey.

A statistically significant difference was found between income levels and scores obtained from the mindfulness dimension of the CS ($Z=-2.112$; $p=0.035$). The study found that participants with income equal to or greater than their expenses had significantly higher mindfulness scores compared to those with income less than expenses. Additionally, a statistically significant difference was observed between income levels and scores on the disengagement dimension of the CS ($Z=-2.655$; $p=0.008$). The disengagement scores of participants with an income less than their expenses were significantly higher than those of participants whose income levels were equal to or greater than their expenses. Finally, there was a statistically significant difference between income level and total CS scores ($t=-2.134$; $p=0.035$). The total CS scores of participants with an income equal to or greater than their expenses were significantly higher than those of participants whose income was less than their expenses (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison of the scores obtained from the scales according to certain descriptive characteristics

	Kindness	Indifference	Conscious sharing	Separation	Conscious awareness	Disengagement	Total	ETS	ATIS
Age									
≤20	16.00±2.52	8.64±3.02	14.87±2.86	7.85±2.61	15.15±2.25	7.93±2.37	93.59±10.74	65.66±7.28	50.37±6.06
>20	15.89±2.72	8.20±2.94	15.20±3.79	7.89±2.14	15.74±2.52	7.37±2.40	95.37±11.04	71.57±8.02	49.00±6.29
Statistical	p=0.833	p=0.403	p=0.368	p=0.809	p=0.31	p=0.228	p=0.435	p<0.001	p=0.161
Region of residence									
Eastern Anatolia	15.25±2.58	9.11±2.91	14.39±3.07	8.64±2.59	14.75±2.43	8.55±2.37	90.09±11.50	67.23±8.88	49.95±5.62
Mediterranean	16.41±2.51	8.23±2.76	15.09±3.16	7.52±2.14	15.64±2.22	7.34±2.21	96.05±8.75	67.68±8.01	49.57±6.76
Others	16.79±2.36	7.36±3.62	16.50±3.41	6.50±2.14	16.36±2.10	6.43±2.21	101.36±9.80	69.14±4.76	50.79±6.04
Statistical	p=0.054	p=0.067	p=0.073	p=0.008	p=0.056	p=0.005	p<0.001	p=0.742	p=0.906
Income level									
Less than expenses	15.25±3.28	9.50±3.74	14.25±3.49	9.38±3.20	13.63±2.13	9.75±2.49	86.50±15.00	68.50±10.07	48.75±5.70
Than expenses	16.02±2.52	8.40±2.92	15.04±3.19	7.73±2.34	15.50±2.32	7.56±2.31	94.86±10.24	67.62±7.88	50.00±6.20
Statistical	p=0.419	p=0.405	p=0.457	p=0.167	p=0.035	p=0.008	p=0.035	p=0.767	p=0.450

The study found a positive and weak correlation between the ATIS scores and the scores obtained from the CS and its dimensions of kindness and common humanity. There was also a negative and weak correlation between the scores obtained from the ATIS and the separation dimension of the CS ($p<0.005$) (Table 3).

Table 3. The relationship between the ATIS, ETS and CS scores

Correlation * (n=102)	ATIS	
	r	p
ETS	-0.028	0.782
CS scales	Kindness	0.243
	Indifference	-0.050
	Conscious sharing	0.218
	Separation	-0.227
	Conscious awareness	0.186
	Disengagement	-0.102
	CS Total	0.253

DISCUSSION

Midwifery practices encompass reproductive health, women's health, and the protection and development of women's, family, and community health during pregnancy, birth, and the postpartum period. Nursing Midwifery Council/NMC has emphasized the importance of nurse care based on compassion, dignity and human rights (Nursing Midwifery Council, 2012). Midwives is a profession that requires a sincere and compassionate approach to providing care while understanding the needs of the individual. Compassion is demonstrated through actions that alleviate suffering. Midwives are the primary healthcare professionals who specialize in this area. Many international organizations related to nursing emphasize the importance of compassion as a fundamental element of midwifery care (Cingöl et al., 2018; Nursing Midwifery Council, 2012).

The mean CS score of the participants was 96.21 ± 10.85 indicating high levels of compassion. Gunduzoglu et al. (2019), Guduk et al. (2022) found that nursing students exhibited high levels of compassion. Seven et al. (2019) found that fourth-year nursing students had higher levels of compassion. Similar to our findings, Kavradım et al. (2019) found that the mean total compassion score of first-year students was high. The findings of our study, consistent with previous research, reveal that first-year students have a high level of compassion. This is a positive result that points to a potential improvement in the quality of nursing care provided to individuals. However, educators can encourage the practice of compassionate nursing care in students by supporting students in clinical practice and being an effective model.

Empathy is an essential aspect of a caring relationship and is crucial for providing quality nursing care. An empathetic approach enables midwives to understand each client's perspective, making it fundamentally important for the provider-patient relationship and improved health outcomes. The study found that the students had a mean ETS total score of 68.65 ± 7.12 , indicating moderate levels of empathy, which is consistent with similar findings in other studies. Karayiannis et al. (2020) found that empathy levels of nursing students were high. Gunel and Avcı (2021), Akin et al. (2021), and Atan (2023) also reported moderate levels of empathy. Considering the moderate levels of empathy among midwifery students, it may be beneficial to organize seminars or add elective courses to the curriculum to enhance empathy levels, particularly for first-year students. It is worth noting that Alhassan (2019) found high levels of empathy in Ghanaian nursing and midwifery students, which may be attributed to differences in population and cultural characteristics.

Infertility is a medical condition that can have psychological effects on couples and cause stigma, which can influence individuals' attitudes. Attitudes towards infertility are influenced by various factors, including age, gender, educational status, occupation, and region of residence. The study found that the mean ATIS score of the students was 49.90 ± 6.15 , indicating positive attitudes towards infertility. The ATIS scores of the Turkish nursing and midwifery students in the studies of Guner Emul et al. (2021) and Cakır et al. (2020) were 47.00 ± 7.82 and 48.59 ± 6.33 , respectively. Similarly, Sorenson et al. (2016) found positive attitudes towards infertility among nursing students abroad. In contrast, Rouche and Forte (2015) reported negative attitudes among students.

Various factors, including age, gender, income status, and the region where students have lived the longest, can influence students' empathy, compassion, and attitudes towards infertility. Our study found that students' ETS scores increased as they aged, which is supported by a similar study (Gunel & Avcı, 2021). The effect of age on empathy levels can be explained with reference to the effects of experience gained with age on the ability to empathize more effectively in interpersonal communication and relationships. The study also found a significant relationship between the separation and disengagement dimensions of the CS and the region of residence. Accordingly, the students from the Eastern Anatolia region of Turkey obtained

significantly higher scores from the separation and disengagement dimensions of the CS. However, total CS scores of these students were significantly lower than students from other regions. This difference may be attributed to variations in personal and cultural values, as well as economic concerns in the predominantly rural Eastern Anatolia region. To enhance compassion and empathy among first-year students, vocational education should focus on providing and strengthening compassion skills. The study also found that students with income levels equal to or greater than their expenses obtained significantly higher scores from the CS and its mindfulness dimension. This finding may be due to the absence of financial worries among individuals with higher income levels, leading to increased self-confidence.

Infertility in Turkey is often perceived as a problem of women. As a result, women are disproportionately impacted by this issue. Infertile individuals require the utmost compassion and empathy from healthcare providers. Health professionals play a crucial role in creating a positive environment and caring for infertile patients at their facilities and compassion and empathy are essential tools for fulfilling these responsibilities. The study found a positive correlation between the ATIS scores and the scores obtained from the CS and its kindness and common humanity dimensions. Conversely, a negative correlation was found between the ATIS scores and the score obtained from the separation dimension of the CS. It is encouraging to see that first-year students are already sensitive to infertility, despite not having taken courses on the topics. This may be because the majority of midwifery students in our study were female and they tended to have stronger communication skills, more prominent emotions such as compassion and pity, and more empathy and compassion skills due to gender norms

CONCLUSION

Infertility is a psychosocial problem that can cause negative emotions such as anxiety, stress, and hopelessness. Couples dealing with this issue often seek empathy and compassion from healthcare professionals. Midwives, who have extended face-to-face communication with women, are often the first professionals consulted by couples experiencing difficulty conceiving. Therefore, it is crucial for midwifery students to demonstrate sensitivity and compassion towards individuals before graduation. Including these topics in the course curriculum can significantly contribute to the development of empathy and compassion in midwifery students' professional lives. This study found that the compassion levels of the first-year midwifery students were high, empathy levels were positive and their attitudes towards infertility were positive.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Author Contributions

Plan, design: TGE, ÇÇD; **Material, methods and data collection:** TGE, ÇÇD, AÇ; **Data analysis and comments:** TGE; **Writing and corrections:** TGE, AÇ, FTC

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